

**Teacher Professional Qualification and Experience: A Requisite for Effective
Classroom Teaching in Banadir Region, Somalia**

by

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Abstract

This paper discussed teachers' professional qualifications and experience as a requisite for effective classroom teaching in the Banadir region, Somalia. The paper discussed teacher

professional qualifications as a person's academic or educational background or certificate that qualifies him or her to work as a teacher in a school and experience as the culmination of skill, exposure or training acquired over time that enables you to perform an existing job better or prepares you for a teaching position, others are years of teaching experience; teachers' mastery of the subject; and teachers' teaching or pedagogical skills as all the necessary cognitive knowledge for making teaching effective and to make suitable learning environments for learners. Several opinions of other authors were reviewed in this paper. The paper holds strongly that effective teaching is basically hinged on professional qualifications, years of teaching experience, subject matter knowledge, and pedagogical content knowledge of the teacher. The paper notes with dismay that many teachers in Somalia still lack these requisite qualities. It was recommended therefore that pre-service teachers should be made to possess these core qualities such as; subject matter knowledge, and pedagogical content knowledge so as to meet up with the current trend in national education. It also recommended that stakeholders in education develop a strategy for monitoring the establishment of related educational institutions in the country to ensure that the standard is not compromised.

Keywords: *Pedagogy, Subject mastery, Teacher experience, Teacher qualification, Teaching skills.*

Introduction

Education forms the crust of sustainable development and is one of the most vital tools in the cumulative excellence of life. The foundation of a great nation is the quality of

its education, and the quality of a good education is behind the professional quality and experience of teachers. Education goals to equip learners with varied basic scientific skills, competence, and creativity are needed to create wealth. These goals will continue to be a mirage if teachers do not have the pre-requisite professional qualifications and experience needed for effective classroom teaching.

Teachers need to be fully equipped with knowledge and skills related to teaching strategies and techniques. Evidence from the literature reveals that teachers' qualifications and experience are important qualities for successful curriculum delivery as it allows effective classroom teaching that is aligned with student needs (Antony et al., 2019).

Teacher qualification refers to academic and professional qualifications that enable a person to become a registered teacher at different levels of education (Filgona & Sakiyo, 2020). Qualified teachers have the knowledge and expertise to teach their classrooms effectively, and they can provide for individual needs. The well-qualified teachers are keen on their profession and love teaching their classrooms.

Teacher experience has to do with the increased awareness of diversifying searches for new ideas, new commitments, and new challenges. Experience and subject-matter skills among teachers are crucial components of effective classroom teaching. Teachers' knowledge, abilities, and productivity improve as they gain experience. Irvine, (2019) supported that teachers who have taken their lessons seriously for years will have appropriate teaching skills, and students will learn more effectively under their guidance. Teacher experience has a significant positive effect on classroom progress, with more than half of the gains occurring during the teachers' first few years, but substantial gains occurring over subsequent years; although, at a slower rate.

In this manner, teacher professional qualification and experience (subject matter knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge) have been linked to being one of the requisites for effective classroom teaching, in this view, it is important to consider the qualifications and expertise of teachers in schools of education since they produce effective classroom teaching. The teacher is the key indicator of effective classroom teaching. As a result, the purpose of this paper is to examine teachers' professional qualifications and experience, which are required for effective classroom teaching in Somalia's Banadir region.

Numerous studies have it that qualification indicators like teachers' subject matter knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and teachers' qualifications and experience are positive requisites for effective classroom teaching, while others have observed the contrary. Some researchers asserted that teachers' knowledge of their classroom has the strongest correlation to their success, whereas others asserted that teachers' teaching.

Concept of Effective Teaching

Effective teaching has emerged as one component that greatly improves learning. Interaction in the classroom is often dominated by the teacher. Teachers are persons who can bring a different educational practice. The quality of their teaching is an important factor in improving effective classroom learning. Effective teaching refers to teaching which successfully achieves students' learning intended by the teacher (Cohen et al., 2020). There are two elements that are considered concerning effective teaching according to Chen, (2017), the must-have clear idea of what learning is to be fostered and the teacher sets up and provides a learning experience that achieves this.

On the other hand, Cohen et al., (2020) stated that effective teaching requires a set of executive skills, and these skills are planning, communicating goals, regulating the activities of the workplace, creating a pleasant environment for work, educating new members of the workgroup, supervising and working with other people, motivating with those being supervised, and evaluating the performance of those being supervised. Most people would agree that good teachers are caring, supportive, concerned about the welfare of the students, knowledgeable about their subject matter, able to get along with parents, and genuinely excited about the work that they do (Burgess, 2019).

In contrast, Harcourt & State, (2019) described key elements of effective teaching in four categories; quality of instruction, appropriate levels of instruction, incentive, and time. Quality of instruction is about the product of quality, organization, and comprehensiveness, of the curriculum and lesson presentation. In the second category, by appropriate levels of instruction, students are ready to learn a new lesson, having the necessary skills, background knowledge, and material that are neither too easy nor too difficult. In the intensive category, students are motivated to work and learn. In the last

category, classroom time is well used with adequate time for learning. All four elements must be attended to effectively if learning is to be accelerated.

A perusal of the relevant literature also provides research findings which investigate teaching according to the considerations of teachers, student teachers, and so on. During their pre-service programs, they looked at whether or not student teachers' attitudes changed. The findings of Harcourt & State, (2019) supported the following key point: (1) student teachers transition from a "teacher-centred" to a "student-centred" vision of instruction. (2) Student teachers transition from a "control" perspective to a comprehensive perspective of classroom management. (3) Relationships with students are seen professionally by student teachers as opposed to personally.

Basic Requisites for Effective Teaching

The basic requisites which contribute to and influence teaching effectiveness has been documented in the literature and effort has continued to be invested in determining the various elements that affect teaching effectiveness. In this section, some identified requisites that determine teaching effectiveness are briefly discussed.

- **Professional qualification:** across the years, the teaching profession which was seen as a noble profession has been taken over by an individual who lacks adequate professional training. Zahoor et al., (2019) reported that the low employment opportunities relevant in most countries, including Somalia, have contributed to the high level of nonprofessional teachers considering teaching as a stop-gap which should be jettisoned as soon as their dream jobs are obtained. Professional teachers are those who possess relevant training in education for their teaching subjects up to all minimum (Filgona & Sakiyo, 2020).

For instance, some teachers are knowledgeable about their subjects, but non-professional teachers are not. Such teachers lack pedagogical knowledge, have low levels of motivation, and may not be overly concerned about their ability to teach effectively. This is probably the case in the Banadir area as the majority of schools are named by people who lack professional qualifications, some of whom are only secondary school graduates.

- **Teaching experience:** this refers to the number of that a person has actively engaged as a teacher in the teaching and learning process. Here, the length of the teacher's

service is used to judge their experience. It is considered that the longer one works in a field, such as teaching, the more experience one accrues and the more informed one learns about what it takes to increase students' academic performance or production. Teachers who have not been teaching for a long time are probably not as successful at providing services there as more experienced teachers. The student's academic success may be impacted by this. This was supported by the findings of the study conducted by Faqih, (2021), which revealed that among teachers in the Banadir region of Somalia, teaching experience was a crucial element that affected the degree of perceived effectiveness among the teachers.

- ***Teacher remuneration:*** remuneration refers to the salaries and benefits overfed to a person on the basis of goal attainment established by the organization. It is expected that the current low teacher count will have a role in the ineffectiveness of the teachers. According to Harcourt & State, (2019), salary adjustments for teachers are expected to have an impact on education quality through two different channels: by impacting both teacher effectiveness and school efficiency. They instinctively reasoned that by lowering teacher turnover, increasing teacher pay may increase school efficiency.

According to research conducted in the United States, teacher turnover might hinder students' ability to learn because it diverts district resources to the hiring process, undermines teacher collaboration, and weakens the relationship or degree of trust between students and teachers Cohen et al., (2020). He pointed out that raising teacher pay might have a direct negative influence on teacher turnover, which would boost a school's effectiveness. Burgess, (2019) discovered that perceptions of adequate or other financial compensation were positively correlated with a number of aspects of teachers' role performance, including lesson presentation, use of instructional materials, and classroom evaluation, among secondary school teachers in the Banadir region.

- ***School facilities and instructional aids:*** the importance of the physical environment in promoting effective teaching has been well captured by scholars and researchers. According to Okogbaa, & Gbogi, (2019), the structure and architecture of the school could encourage some educational methods while discouraging others, as well as having a big impact on the discipline. The process of constructing building facilities should be based on the desired curricular programs as designers, architects, and school

administrators create future schools and learning spaces for the expanding school population. The attending populations could be included in this, and the design of these learning processes should primarily be guided by the existing technologies. In basic terms, the facilities should have been designed to fit the intended curriculum and use. School facilities are libraries, textbooks, chalkboards, pens and other items which make the teaching-learning process possible and easier.

While some scholars such as Hassan & Wekesa, (2017) argued that although a skilled teacher can teach anywhere and a determined student can learn regardless of the environment, the social environment is crucial and should not be underestimated. It is a basic fact that the educational setting itself possesses significant unrealized potential as an active facilitator of learning. There are resources available in every society besides schools that can aid in the teaching and learning process. Learners must have access to the required knowledge, tools, and resources for learning to occur. In order to guarantee an acceptable level of performance, they must interact with both tangible and intangible resources and processes.

- ***Teacher-student ratio:*** student-teacher ratio is the number of students who attend a specific educational institution divided by the number of teachers in that institution. For example, a student-teacher ratio of 10:1 indicates that there are ten students for one teacher. Another way to express the term is as a teacher-to-student ratio. According to Cohen et al., (2020), all students gain from smaller classes because teachers can give each student more individualized attention, although low-achieving kids benefit more at secondary schools.
- ***Institutional leadership:*** in most human interactions, the influence of leadership on behavior and performance has been adequately documented. The school's status as a social institution rests, like other organizations, on how its leaders behave. There are a variety of leadership philosophies that can be used depending on the circumstance, but there are three main ones: authoritarian, democratic, and laissez-faire (Omar, 2017). There is no agreement on the best leadership style, despite extensive studies on the extent to which leaders exhibit certain types and their impact on productivity. Dutta & Hazarika, (2021) discovered that democratic teaching methods are most effective in the schools. In a related finding, Hassan & Wekesa, (2017) found that the laissez-faire

leadership style, in addition to the democratic leadership style, had a significant positive impact on the work efficacy of senior school teachers in the teaching.

Teachers' Qualifications for Effective Classroom Teaching

A teaching qualification is defined as a person's academic or educational background or certificate that qualifies him or her to work as a teacher in a school (Uddin et al., 2019). Traditional and alternative qualification paths are used to qualify teachers. When an individual completes an undergraduate degree or graduate program in education, they are traditionally certified.

Alternative certification paths rely on coursework in pedagogy and subject areas rather than a degree in education. As alternatives to formal qualifications, short-term activities like peer reviews, workshops, and mentoring can help teachers become more effective in the classroom (Zahoor et al., 2019). If they are unable to immediately find another job, more recent college graduates who have first-degree content go into classroom teaching. This could affect such teachers' ability to teach effectively in the classroom.

Aloysius, (2021) undertook a study and found that after training, there was a large increase in the number of classroom teaching tactics that teachers believed to be effective, suggesting that the training was successful in raising teachers' expertise in classroom teaching. After training, the number of proactive strategies was viewed by teachers as being more useful for classroom teaching than reactive strategies, which stayed unchanged. Hence, a quick one-day in-service training can significantly alter teachers' knowledge of efficient classroom teaching approaches. Leibur et al., (2021) reported that educational background significantly impacted teachers' effectiveness in the classroom. Most educational scholars encourage all teachers, male and female, regardless of their area of specialization in education, must acquire a suitable level of professional qualification enabling them to perform effective classroom teaching in order to improve their ability to do so. For efficient classroom instruction in the Banadir region of Somalia, teachers' professional qualifications and experience (teachers' subject-matter expertise and pedagogical expertise) are crucial.

Teachers' Years of Teaching Experience for Effective Classroom Teaching

Teaching experience refers to the culmination of skill, exposure or training acquired over time that enables you to perform an existing job better or prepares you for a teaching position (Berger et al., 2018). Teaching experience is important to the development of a unique teaching style teaching skill and self-confidence. Irvine, (2019) stated that efficacy is a skill that can be acquired through training and many years of experience in the field.

Experienced teachers recognize the establishment of effective classroom teaching as one of the major goals to be accomplished in the first week of the year (Irvine, 2019). However, several researches indicate that beginning and experienced teachers differ in their approaches to effective classrooms. Student teachers are unduly preoccupied with maintaining order in the classroom and have switched the emphasis of their planning from activities meant to promote learning to those that are more likely to prevent disruption.

On the other hand, experienced teachers may adopt practices that cause the learning environment to suffer (Berger et al., 2018). Years of teaching experience have a favorable effect on a teacher's ability to keep a positive learning environment in the classroom. Ademola et al., (2021) revealed in one of their findings that the efficacy of teachers' classroom teaching was significantly influenced by their years of teaching experience. (Onwuegbuzie & Carter, 2021) observed that teachers showed significantly different attitudes toward the behavior and instructional management subscales of classroom learning based on their years of teaching experience. Less experienced teachers were shown to be interactionists on each measure, whereas more experienced teachers consistently scored as interventionists. Issue of the classroom teaching is the area in which administrators expressed the greatest concern regarding new teachers' classroom skills.

Teachers' Subject Matter Knowledge for Effective Classroom Teaching

Subject matter knowledge of the teacher is essential and steamily critical for effective classroom teaching. Subject mastery provides the teacher with an understanding of the content he/she is teaching to improve effective classroom teaching Amalu et al., (2020). Teachers' subject matter knowledge may be affected by the attitudes and expectations that their students bring to classroom teaching. Teachers' understanding of subject matter affects their capacity to simplify content to help students understand.

Research of teacher knowledge indicated that teachers' knowledge of the matter influences effective classroom teaching/learning success across subject areas and at diverse grade levels (Kiamba et al., 2017). Without the essential base of the subject matter knowledge, teachers are merely incapable to produce effective classroom teaching. Teachers' knowledge of the subject matter content is a particularly significant issue in classroom teaching, as nationwide studies steadily report that many teachers have inadequate training in subject matter knowledge disciplines. Subject mastery influences the learner's understanding of the subject they learn, performance and eventual attainment of the national goals. The above discussion supports a positive relationship between teachers' subject mastery and effective classroom teaching.

Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge for Effective Classroom Teaching

Teachers from countries that are top performers in effective classroom teaching tend to have more opportunities to learn pedagogical content. Research has made it clear that teachers' pedagogical knowledge powers their classroom teaching. Researchers have also argued that pedagogical knowledge serves as a foundation for the development of effective classroom teaching. Pedagogical content knowledge refers to the unique knowledge of teaching possessed by teachers, the particular form of content knowledge that embodies the aspects of content most germane to its teachability in effective classroom teaching (Ulferts, 2019).

The pedagogical knowledge of a teacher includes all the necessary cognitive knowledge for making teaching effective and to make suitable learning environments for learners. Odumosu et al., (2018) described that pedagogical content knowledge is the integration of four types of teacher knowledge: subject matter knowledge, knowledge of pedagogy, knowledge of students, and knowledge of environmental contexts. Pedagogical content knowledge covers conceptual and procedural knowledge and the stages of understanding that teachers are likely to pass through in moving from a state of having little understanding to mastery of it.

Teachers require pedagogical knowledge insight classroom teaching to communicate their subject knowledge effectively and impact students significantly. Pedagogical expertise incorporates wisdom related to the teaching and learning process, as

well as the dynamic between student needs and content demands. Pedagogical experience yields a variety of instructional techniques that allow teachers to share their subject matter knowledge with students in the classroom. Teachers draw on pedagogical and subject matter understanding to respond to common misconceptions about the content area; address challenging aspects of the learning acquisitions; and accommodate prior knowledge, experience, and skill that students at different developmental levels typically bring to the classroom.

Every teacher has a different pedagogical approach of skill to teaching in his/her classroom. Ulferts, (2019), argued that teachers, require a variety of pedagogical strategies to suit a variety of situations in effective classroom teaching. Badsah, (2021) asserted that pedagogical content knowledge depends on the teacher's subject matter knowledge, knowledge of pedagogy, and how she or he transforms that knowledge into the various forms that enable students in different learning environments to understand the subject matter.

Odumosu et al., (2018) has documented that pedagogical content knowledge as one of the most important knowledge bases that teachers should process to teach effectively in the classroom. In general, pedagogical knowledge affects how teachers think about their subject matter knowledge. A skilled and very knowledgeable teacher has the potential to make the learning of the subject more meaningful through effective classroom teaching. Teachers with student knowledge will ensure the appropriateness of the content and instructional strategies used in their classroom teaching. Teachers with student knowledge will ensure that the content and instructional strategies used in their classroom teaching are appropriate.

Problems of Ineffective Teaching on Students' Learning

Evidence in the literature shows that ineffective teaching and learning is traceable to some factors such as unqualified and experienced teachers, inadequate teachers, class size, voluminous curriculum content, poor preparation of textbooks, shortage or poor equipment/materials for teaching, poor motivation of the teachers, use of inappropriate teaching methods, lack of practical activities amongst the others (Mupa & Isaac, 2015). These ineffective teaching problems hinder students from achieving their learning goals,

reduce student engagement in the classroom, diminish the quality of teachers' feedback to students, and deteriorate teachers' relationships with families.

Strategies for Improving Teaching Effectiveness in Somalia

Policymakers in Somalia can invest in the following to tackle the main challenges and to build better teaching effectiveness. According to MOECHE, (2017), the following are some strategies for teaching effectiveness in Somalia:

- ❖ ***Preparing teachers better;*** establish open management of the nation's preservice institutions. Making certification a continual process and carrying out independent audits can help to improve the regulation of preservice institutions. Include important practical components in the degree program for teaching. Preservice institutions should change their curricula frequently. Enhance the teacher eligibility design.
- ❖ ***Ensuring teachers high-quality professional development once hire;*** training should be tailored to address issues like learning level heterogeneity in the classroom. Target training based on teacher needs and make it practical with a subject-specific focus. Organize in-service training in conjunction with rewards to increase teachers' engagement and effort. In order to guide future training, evaluate the effectiveness of the program's implementation.
- ❖ ***Providing continuous feedback and support to teachers;*** invest in regular post-training follow-ups with teachers and continued coaching investments. Use cluster resource coordinators and block education officials to give follow-ups regarding in-service training.
- ❖ ***Establishing transparent systems to hold teachers accountable for performance;*** to more effectively hold teachers accountable, evaluate their performance and keep an eye on it. Integrate teacher effectiveness with career development, and create a clear path for professional development. Performance incentives are short-term expenses that conceders cover.
- ❖ ***Improving teacher management processes;*** improve quality and design of existing data systems to improve transparency and efficiency. Prepare situational suitable leadership style for school leading.
- ❖ ***Using data to guide policy;*** to get a current and comprehensive understanding of teachers in government schools today, gather primary data on their practices, knowledge, and attitudes. Use administrative data as well as routine sample-based

surveys to better understand the circumstances of different schools and tailor policy accordingly.

Conclusion

This paper exposed that teachers' qualifications and experience are key variables required for effective classroom teaching. It has also shown that their quality and experience are crucial prerequisites for attaining educational goals and objectives. It is, therefore, not out of place for the Somali National Policy On Education (RFN 2016) to have remarkably stated that no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Teachers, therefore, need to continuously seek ways of improving their professional qualifications and experience (subject matter knowledge and pedagogical knowledge) to improve the positive requisites for effective classroom teaching.

Recommendations

In light of the conclusion, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Teacher education should be replacing this word in all teacher education institutions. It is necessary to ensure pre-service teachers' subject matter knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge are adequate and meet up with the current trend in national education.
2. To ensure that the standard is not compromised, educational stakeholders should develop a strategy for monitoring the spread of related educational institutions in the country.
3. All educational stakeholder officials should always make an effort to engage the services of those qualified and experienced teachers in the field.
4. All teacher training institutions should admit only those who meet the prerequisite requirements to teach effectively in the classroom.

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